

Received: January 04, 2026 | Revised: January 15, 2026 | Accepted: January 19, 2026 | Published: January 25, 2026

Dynamics of a Mathematical Model for Four-State Binocular Rivalry

Yun jiao Wang, PhD ¹, Franchell Davison ², Eniola Bankole ³

¹ Assistant Professor Texas Southern, University Department of Mathematics, United States of America

² Assistant Professor Texas Southern, University Department of Mathematics, United States of America

³ Assistant Professor Texas Southern, University Department of Mathematics, United States of America

Corresponding author: **Yun jiao Wang**

Abstract

Binocular rivalry is a visual perception phenomenon in which the percept alternates between several different images while the stimuli remain unchanged. This phenomenon has long been utilized to study visual awareness and its underlying cortical mechanisms. Many works on perceptual rivalry focus on bistable perceptual rivalry while only a minuscule amount of work considers rivalry between more than two percepts (multistable perceptual rivalry). However, multistable perceptual rivalry offers more tools for studying our brain than the bistable case. Here we study a model that accounts for quadra-state binocular rivalry observed in several sets of experiments. We find that both slow adaptation and noise are needed to produce stochastic switching. We have also provided a different view on the source of the four percepts from dynamical system aspect.

Keywords: Perception, multistable, binocular rivalry and mathematics

1. Introduction

Our visual system excels at processing received information and usually forms a stable percept. However, when two distinct images are presented to different eyes simultaneously, the information from one eye conflicts that from another eye. As a result, our brain has a difficult time processing and making sense of the information. In this situation, instead of seeing a fused image, one experiences perception switching stochastically between two (bistable) or more different percepts (multistable) every few seconds. Such phenomenon is called binocular rivalry [20, 1]. The interesting feature of dynamic perception under constant stimuli makes binocular rivalry an excellent tool for studying cortical mechanisms underlying awareness [10, 19, 17, 11, 14].

Research related to binocular rivalry has a long history. Sir Charles Wheatstone performed the first systematic experiment on binocular rivalry in 1838 [20] by using a device of his own invention-later known as the stereoscope. Since his work, a huge body of literature has been devoted to binocular rivalry. Among those, most works focus on the binocular rivalry between two percepts (bistable binocular rivalry). It is believed that three mechanisms are responsible for the stochastic switching behavior: mutual inhibition between neuronal populations associated to the two percepts, noise, and adaptation. Several rate models based on the mechanisms in the form of mutual inhibitory two-node network as shown in Fig. 1 were proposed and are to capture the dynamics observed in experiments on bistable binocular rivalry [21, 16, 9, 13, 7, 12, 15]. However, such models cannot explain binocular rivalry interocular grouping.

Figure 1: Mutual inhibitory network model where the arrows represent inhibitions from the tail nodes to the head nodes.

Kovacs et al. [8] showed that when presented two intermingle images of monkey face and jungle scene as shown in Fig. 2(b) to different eyes, one perceived not only the presented images, but also the two coherent images in Fig. 2(a). On the other hand, if the whole monkey face presented to one eye and the jungle scene to the another, one only perceives the two presented images. This set of experiments demonstrates that our brain groups the information based on the affinity among pieces of information due to the same eye origin and as well as to certain coherent traits. The mutual inhibitory two-node model cannot account for such regrouping process.

Figure 2: Stimulus (a) leads to rivalry between the two images. The intermingle images in (b) can lead to rivalry between all four images: the two images in (a) and the two images in (b) [8].

Diekman et al. [4] proposed a four-node network model that is based on the three mechanisms mentioned earlier and recurrent excitation couplings due to the same eye origin and interocular grouping due to coherent traits. They associated patterns of oscillations that can be obtained through Hopf bifurcation with these percepts: the percepts of presented images associated to patterns of a branch of limit cycles and the percepts of interocular grouped ones with the patterns of a different branch of limit cycles. However, they did not show whether it was possible to have stochastic switching between all four percepts when noises are added to the model. Unlike bistable case in which stochasticity can be easily obtained by adding white noises to a system, numerical study showed that adding white noises to the model in [4] doesn't usually show the desired stochastic switches even with very large noises. The goal of this paper is to study the dynamics of the model and investigate the possibility of stochastic switching, and if yes, what the possible range of parameter values is.

One feature of the models for binocular rivalry is that they are fast-slow systems. In this paper, we study the whole system by first understanding the fast system of the model. We found numerically and analytically that in certain parameter range, the fast system possesses four stable equilibria associated to the four percepts. We then show numerically that with noises generated by OU process, stochastic switching among the four percepts can occur. In addition, we gave a different view on the occurrence of the patterns associated to the percepts from the dynamical system point of view.

2. The Model

The network model in [4] is shown in Fig. 2 where node x_{11} represents neural population associated to the patches of a monkey face from the left eye, node x_{22} represents neural population associated to the patches of jungle scene from the left eye, node x_{12} represents neural population associated to the patches of monkey face from the right eye, node x_{21} represents neural population associated to the patches of jungle scene from the right eye. The solid arrows (between x_{11} and x_{22} , and between x_{12} and x_{21}) are recurrent excitations due to the same eye origin; the dashed arrows are the interocular grouping due to the similar texture among the image patches; the remaining two arrows represent inhibitory coupling between populations in the same hemifield.

Figure 3: The network by Diekman et al. in [4]

Each node in the network is described by two variables: E_{ij} (for $i, j=1,2$) are the firing rate variables and

H_{ij} are the adaptation rate variables describing hyperpolarizing currents that are activated due to increases in firing rates. The equations associated to the network are in the form of (2.1), where $\tau \ll \tau_b$, I_i are the external input strengths from the stimuli, here we assume that all are the same for all four nodes, and φ is the strength of adaptation rate.

$$\tau E_{11} = -E_{11} + G(I_1 + \alpha E_{22} + \beta E_{12} - \omega E_{21} - \varphi H_{11}) \quad (2.1a)$$

$$\tau_b H_{11} = E_{11} - H_{11} \quad (2.1b)$$

$$\tau E_{12} = -E_{12} + G(I_2 + \alpha E_{21} + \beta E_{11} - \omega E_{22} - \varphi H_{12}) \quad (2.1c)$$

$$\tau_b H_{12} = E_{12} - H_{12} \quad (2.1d)$$

$$\tau E_{21} = -E_{21} + G(I_3 + \alpha E_{12} + \beta E_{22} - \omega E_{11} - \varphi H_{21}) \quad (2.1e)$$

$$\tau_b H_{21} = E_{21} - H_{21} \quad (2.1f)$$

$$\tau E_{22} = -E_{22} + G(I_4 + \alpha E_{11} + \beta E_{21} - \omega E_{12} - \varphi H_{22}) \quad (2.1g)$$

$$\tau_b H_{22} = E_{22} - H_{22} \quad (2.1h)$$

Eye-based excitatory coupling is parameterized by α ; β parameterizes excitation that facilitates interocular grouping; and ω parameterizes mutual inhibition due to conflict information in the same hemifield. The nonlinear gain function G which models the relationship between a population's inputs and its output firing rate is chosen to be a sigmoidal function where a , b , and θ are constant positive real numbers.

For a given state, the dominant percept is associated with the two populations with the highest firing rates. We say at time t the monkey face in the model is dominant if $E_{11}(t) > E_{21}(t)$ and $E_{12}(t) > E_{22}(t)$. Similarly, the percept of the jungle scene is dominant if $E_{21}(t) > E_{11}(t)$ and $E_{22}(t) > E_{12}(t)$; the percept of the left eye image is dominant if $E_{21}(t) > E_{11}(t)$ and $E_{12}(t) > E_{22}(t)$; the percept of the right eye image is dominant if $E_{11}(t) > E_{21}(t)$ and $E_{12}(t) > E_{22}(t)$. For convenience, we refer to the presented images as percepts 1 and 2 and interocular grouped images as percepts 3 and 4.

3. Dynamics of a fast system

Among the three mechanisms (mutual inhibition, adaptation and noise), adaptation and noise are believed to be responsible for percept switching while mutual inhibition accounts for the suppression of other percepts. This indicates that without adaptation (adaptation = 0) and noise, the system should have four stable equilibria. Also note that because of the relation between the two-time constants: $\tau \ll \tau h$, the system (2.1) is a fast-slow system with E_{ij} being fast variables and H_{ij} being slow variables. That means in the fast time scale, we can study the system by treating H_{ij} as a constant (i.e. studying the fast system), which makes the studying the equilibrium states of the fast system with $H_{ij}(t) = 0$ meaningful.

The fast system we are interested in is the system (5.5).

$$\tau E_{11} = -E_{11} + G(I + \alpha E_{22} + \beta E_{12} - \omega E_{21}) \quad (3.3a)$$

$$\tau E_{12} = -E_{12} + G(I + \alpha E_{21} + \beta E_{11} - \omega E_{22}) \quad (3.3b)$$

$$\tau E_{21} = -E_{21} + G(I + \alpha E_{12} + \beta E_{22} - \omega E_{11}) \quad (3.3c)$$

$$\tau E_{22} = -E_{22} + G(I + \alpha E_{11} + \beta E_{21} - \omega E_{12}) \quad (3.3d)$$

System (5.5) has D_2 symmetry and the isotypic decomposition of R^4 is:

$$V_1 = \{E_{11} = E_{21} = E_{12} = E_{22}\}$$

$$V_2 = \{E_{11} = E_{12}, E_{21} = E_{22}, E_{11} = -E_{21}\}$$

$$V_3 = \{E_{11} = E_{21}, E_{12} = E_{22}, E_{11} = -E_{12}\}$$

$$V_4 = \{E_{11} = E_{22}, E_{12} = E_{21}, E_{11} = -E_{21}\}$$

Note that a synchrony breaking steady-state bifurcation in V_1 and V_3 leads to equilibrium states in which the conflict information from the left and right eyes is superimposed, a synchrony breaking steady-state bifurcation in V_2 leads to steady-states associated to percepts of the two presented images and bifurcation in V_4 leads to steady-states associated to percepts of the two mixed-eye images, i.e. the four percepts are associated to the four steady-states of the fast system. By using a numerical bifurcation computation package AUTO [5] that was built in XPPAUT [6] to obtain bifurcation diagram of the system as shown in Fig. 4 Red curves are branches of stable equilibria and black curves are unstable equilibria. When fixing the coupling of same eye origin $\alpha = 0.5$ and decreasing the value of the interocular coupling β , the branches of equilibria associated to percepts 3 and 4 become less and less stable and lose their stability when $\beta = 0.21$. On the other hand, if we increase β , the branches of equilibria associated to percepts 3 and 4 become more and more stable while the branches of equilibria associated to percepts 1 and 2 become less stable and lose their stability at $\beta = 0.67$.

4. When the gain function is a step function

The model we discussed above consists of smooth ordinary differential equations (ODEs), and the advantage for this type of ODEs is that we can use traditional bifurcation theory and existing numerical software to obtain bifurcation diagrams. On the other hand, if the gain function G in the System (2.1) takes the form of a step function, then the system becomes piecewise linear, which makes it possible to

Figure 4: Bifurcation diagram with β being the bifurcation parameter and $\alpha = 0.5$ remains constant.

solve system analytically. Moreover, a step function can be approximated by smooth sigmoidal functions as close as we need. That is, the analysis to the system with the gain functions taking the form of step functions can provide useful information for the understanding of the dynamics of the network system. With this consideration, we assume G in this section to be in the form of where $\theta \geq 0$ is a constant. Seely and Chow [15] have considered such form for bistable binocular rivalry. Here we show that it can be used to explain the four-state perceptual rivalry as well.

$$G(x) \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq \theta \\ 1, & x > \theta \end{cases}$$

We will begin with the fast system (5.5).

Lemma 4.1 When $I + \alpha + \beta > \omega + \theta$, the state $(1,1,1,1)$ is a stable equilibrium state of the system (5.5). Otherwise, $(1,1,1,1)$ is not an equilibrium.

Proof. When $I + \alpha + \beta > \omega + \theta$, substituting $(1,1,1,1)$ into the right-hand side of (5.5) arrives at zero vector. Also, in a small neighborhood of the state, the system is linear with Jacobian matrix $= -\mathbf{I}$ (-identity matrix). So $(1,1,1,1)$ is stable.

Lemma 4.2 When the four states $(1,0,0,1)$, $(0,1,1,0)$, $(1,1,0,0)$ and $(0,0,1,1)$ that corresponds to precepts 1, 2, 3, and 4 are stable steady-states of the fast system (5.5). ◇

$$\theta < I + \alpha < \omega + \theta$$

$$\theta < I + \beta < \omega + \theta$$

Remark: There is a wide range of parameter values satisfy the conditions.

Proof. Consider the state $(1, 0, 0, 1)$. Substituting $E11 = 1, E22 = 1, E12 = E21 = 0$ into the right hand side of (5.5), we have

$$-1 + G(I + \alpha) = 0 \quad -0 + G(I + \beta - \omega) = 0$$

$$-0 + G(I + \beta - \omega) = 0$$

$$-1 + G(I + \alpha) = 0$$

$$\text{Here } G(I + \alpha) = 1 \text{ since } I + \alpha > \theta$$

$$\text{Here } G(I + \beta - \omega) = 0 \text{ since } I + \beta - \omega < \theta$$

Hence $(1, 0, 0, 1)$ is an equilibrium. Note that near the equilibrium, the system becomes the linear system (4.4)

$$\tau E11 = -E11 + 1 \quad (4.4a)$$

$$\tau E12 = -E12 \quad (4.4b)$$

$$\tau E21 = -E21 \quad (4.4c)$$

$$\tau E22 = -E22 + 1 \quad (4.4d)$$

Since the Jacobian at the equilibrium is $-I$ here I is an identity matrix, the equilibrium is stable. By symmetry, we can deduce that the other three states are also stable equilibria of the system (5.5).

Theorem 4.3 Suppose $I > \theta$ and $I + \alpha + \beta < \omega + \theta$, then the four states $(1, 0, 0, 1)$, $(0, 1, 1, 0)$, $(1, 1, 0, 0)$, and $(0, 0, 1, 1)$, that correspond to Precepts 1, 2, 3, and 4 are the only stable equilibria.

Proof. Lemmas 4.1 and 4.2 imply that the four states $(1, 1, 0, 0)$, $(0, 0, 1, 1)$, $(1, 0, 0, 1)$, and $(0, 1, 1, 0)$ are stable equilibria and $(1, 1, 1, 1)$ is not. The remaining proof is to show that the other 11 states cannot be steady states. We prove in four classes: I) $(1, 0, 1, 0)$ and $(0, 1, 0, 1)$; II) only one component is 1: $(1, 0, 0, 0)$, $(0, 1, 0, 0)$, $(0, 0, 1, 0)$, and $(0, 0, 0, 1)$; III) only one component is 0: $(1, 1, 1, 0)$, $(1, 1, 0, 1)$, $(1, 0, 1, 1)$ and $(0, 1, 1, 1)$. Since points in each class are symmetric, we only need to prove one from each class. IV) $(0, 0, 0, 0)$.

Case I: $(1, 0, 1, 0)$ is not an equilibrium since at the state

$$\tau E_{11} = -1 + G(I - \omega) = -1 \neq 0$$

since $G(I - \omega) = 0$ and $I - \omega < I + \alpha - \omega < \theta$.

Case II: $(1, 0, 0, 0)$ is not an equilibrium since at the state:

$$\tau E_{22} = -E_{22} + G(I + \alpha E_{11} + \beta E_{21} - \omega E_{12}) = G(I + \alpha) = 1 \neq 0$$

because $I + \alpha > \theta$.

Case III: $(1, 1, 1, 0)$ is not an equilibrium since at the state:

$$\tau E_{21} = -E_{21} + G(I + \alpha E_{12} + \beta E_{22} - \omega E_{11}) = -1 + G(I + \alpha - \omega) = -1$$

since $I + \alpha < \theta + \omega$.

Case IV: $(0, 0, 0, 0)$ is not an equilibrium since at the state:

$$\tau E_{11} = -E_{11} + G(I + \alpha E_{22} + \beta E_{12} - \omega E_{12}) = -0 + G(I) = 1 \neq 0$$

because $I > \theta$. ◇

While the numerical bifurcation analysis in Section 3 provides the parameter range of β for the fast system having equilibria with the desired patterns, the results in this section on the other hand offer guidance on how to choose the value of parameters α, β, θ and ω in order for the system to having the right set of equilibria. That is, the results in this section provide for a much larger region of parameter values for the four types of equilibria to coexist. For example, in order to observe all the four percepts to occur, we can choose both $\alpha = 0.5, \beta = 0.4, I = 0.5, \theta = 0.5$ and $\omega = 1$ which satisfy the condition in Theorem 4.3. Because the analysis in this section was carried out when the gain functions were in the form of step functions, the application of the result to a system with a smooth gain function will be limited. However, it still gives a rather good guidance when the gain function is steep enough, which is usually the case for the binocular rivalry models.

Stochastic dynamics

Next, we choose the parameter value sets so that the fast system possesses four stable equilibria. Then, add noises that models random fluctuations due to network effects and synaptic noise to the equations of

E_{ij} as follows:

$$\tau E_{11} = -E_{11} + G(I + \alpha E_{22} + \beta E_{12} - \omega E_{21} - \phi H_{11} + n_1) \quad (5.5a)$$

$$\tau E_{12} = -E_{12} + G(I + \alpha E_{21} + \beta E_{11} - \omega E_{22} - \phi H_{12} + n_2) \quad (5.5b)$$

$$\tau E_{21} = -E_{21} + G(I + \alpha E_{12} + \beta E_{22} - \omega E_{11} - \phi H_{21} + n_3) \quad (5.5c)$$

$$\tau E_{22} = -E_{22} + G(I + \alpha E_{11} + \beta E_{21} - \omega E_{12} - \phi H_{22} + n_4) \quad (5.5d)$$

The noises n_i are Ornstein-Uhlenbeck, where $\tau_S = 200ms, \sigma = 0.07$, and $\xi(t)$ is a white-noise process with zero mean. The specific type of noise chosen for n_i does not impact the results significantly, as long as it is a continuous process. Now, in the whole system, the switching among the four percepts occurs. In order to enable us to easily see perceptual dominance, we plot the following quantities in Fig 5 (Upper)

$E_{11}E_{22}$ (associated to percept 1 since percept 1 occurs when both E_{11} and E_{22} dominate), $E_{12}E_{21}$ (associated to percept 2), $E_{11}E_{12}$ (associated to percept 3) and $E_{21}E_{22}$ (associated to percept 4). The distribution of dominance duration follows unimodal distribution.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we explored the possibility of using a four-node network to model four-stable perceptual rivalry. Different from the work in [4,2], we associated the four percepts with four steady-states of the system only consists of firing rate equations which are the fast equations instead of patterns of oscillations as in [4]. Our interpretation matches a widely discussed energy well type of idea that was mentioned in paper [18]. The model is the first to realize the stochastic switches among four percepts with a four-node network structure.

4. Acknowledgement

FD and EB were supported by summer under graduation research program (SURP) at the COSET, Texas Southern University. YW was supported by Seed grant from Texas Southern University and DHS-14-ST- 062-001 award from Department of Homeland Security.

Figure 5: (Upper) An example of time series. (Bottom) Dominance distribution follows unimodal distribution.

6. References

- [1] Blake, R., & Logothetis, N. K. (2002). Visual competition. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 3*, 13–21.
- [2] Diekmann, C. O., & Golubitsky, M. (2013). Constructing rivalry networks for binocular rivalry experiments. *In preparation*.*
- [3] Diekmann, C. O., Golubitsky, M., & McMillen, T. (2012). Reduction and dynamics of a generalized rivalry network with two learned patterns. *SIAM Journal on Applied Dynamical Systems*, 11*, 1270–1309.
- [4] Diekmann, C. O., Golubitsky, M., & Wang, Y. (2013). Derived patterns in binocular rivalry networks. *Journal of Mathematical Neuroscience*, 3*.
- [5] Doedel, E., Paffenroth, R., Champneys, A., Fairgrieve, T., Kuznetsov, Y., Oldeman, B., Sandstede, B., & Wang, X. (2000). *AUTO 2000: Software for continuation and bifurcation problems in ordinary differential equations** (Technical report).
- [6] Ermentrout, B. (2002). *Simulating, analyzing, and animating dynamical systems: A guide to XPPAUT for researchers and students**. SIAM.
- [7] Freeman, A. W. (2005). Multistage model for binocular rivalry. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 94*, 4412–4420.
- [8] Kovács, I., Pápathomas, T. V., Yang, M., & Fehér, A. (1996). When the brain changes its mind: Interocular grouping during binocular rivalry. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 93*, 15508–15511.
- [9] Laing, C., & Chow, C. C. (2002). A spiking neuron model for binocular rivalry. *Journal of Computational Neuroscience*, 12*, 39–53.
- [10] Leopold, D. A., & Logothetis, N. K. (1996). Activity changes in early visual cortex reflect monkeys' percepts during binocular rivalry. *Nature*, 379*, 549–553.
- [11] Leopold, D. A., & Logothetis, N. K. (1999). Multistable phenomena: Changing views in perception. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 3*, 254–264.
- [12] Moldakarimov, S., Rollenhagen, J. E., Olson, C. R., & Chow, C. C. (2005). Competitive dynamics in cortical responses to visual stimuli. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 94*, 3388–3396.
- [13] Moreno-Bote, R., Rinzel, J., & Rubin, N. (2007). Noise-induced alterations in an attractor network model of perceptual bistability. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 98*, 1125–1139.
- [14] Polonsky, A., Blake, R., Braun, J., & Heeger, D. (2000). Neuronal activity in human primary visual cortex correlates with perception during binocular rivalry. *Nature Neuroscience*, 3*, 1153–1159.
- [15] Seely, J., & Chow, C. C. (2011). The role of mutual inhibition in binocular rivalry. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 106*, 2136–2150.
- [16] Shpiro, A., Curtu, R., Rinzel, J., & Rubin, N. (2007). Dynamical characteristics common to neuronal competition models. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 97*, 462–473.
- [17] Sterzer, P., Kleinschmidt, A., & Rees, G. (2009). The neural bases of multistable perception. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 13*.
- [18] Suzuki, S., & Grabowecky, M. (2002). Evidence for perceptual “trapping” and adaptation in multistable binocular rivalry. *Neuron*, 36*, 143–157.
- [19] Tong, F., Meng, M., & Blake, R. (2006). Neural bases of binocular rivalry. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 10*.
- [20] Wheatstone, C. (1838). Contributions to the physiology of vision. Part I. On some remarkable, and hitherto unobserved, phenomena of binocular vision. *London and Edinburgh Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science*, 3*, 241–267.
- [21] Wilson, H. R. (2003). Computational evidence for a rivalry hierarchy in vision. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 100*, 14499–14503.